

NDC ASPECTS

Country Report

Transition pathways for Türkiye

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Key messages

- Türkiye became Party to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change in 2004 and to the Kyoto Protocol in 2009. Türkiye ratified the Paris Agreement in 2021 and in October of the same year announced the 2053 carbon neutrality goal.
- The decarbonization of an emerging, highly industrialized economy like Türkiye, with sustained rates of economic growth and rising population is feasible, albeit challenging.
- The implementation of NDC and long-term decarbonization should be guided by targeted policies and regulatory framework that encourages investments in energy efficiency, renewable power and disruptive clean energy technologies. The sectors that offer the biggest “bang for the buck” are the buildings and the power supply sectors.
- The role of hydrogen, as an energy carrier, is crucial for decarbonizing energy uses. It takes advantage of existing infrastructure and is used in processes hard to decarbonize, such as steel and cement industry.

Introduction and overview

Türkiye is one of the twenty largest economies in the world with a gross domestic product (GDP) of US\$1.024 trillion as of 2023 and a GDP per capita of about US\$ 12,500. Real GDP growth averaged 5.4% between 2002 and 2022, a fact that propelled the country to the upper-middle-income status. Even during the COVID crisis, Türkiye’s economy grew by 1.8% in 2020 - the 2nd highest rate amongst G20 countries, after China [1].

The Turkish energy mix relies predominantly on fossil fuels (85%), higher than the G20 average (82%), as of 2021. Türkiye has significant renewable energy potential, and the utilization of this potential has been increasing over the last decade with investment in wind, hydro and solar PV capacities.

Türkiye’s greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions increased by 133% in the period 1990 – 2018 following its GDP growth and the lack of ambitious climate policies and environmental regulation. The energy sector makes up three quarters of the total emissions. The carbon intensity of the energy sector has remained over 60 tCO₂/TJ since 1990, slightly higher than the G20 average, due to the continuously high share of fossil fuels in the energy mix [2].

Climate change impacts are already present in Türkiye. According to the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) [3], Türkiye is about to experience more frequent and severe weather conditions throughout the year, such as rising temperatures, heatwaves and droughts. Türkiye submitted to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) the updated Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC) in April 2023, pledging to reduce the economy wide GHG emissions by 41% in 2030 compared to its predefined Business-as-Usual scenario, to peak its emissions at the latest in 2038, and achieve a net zero target by 2053.

Key socio-economic figures and outlook

The macroeconomic and population outlook builds on recent demographic and economic projections provided by the United Nations (UN), the International Monetary Fund (IMF), the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) and the World Bank [4-7]. According to the UN world population prospects, Türkiye’s population will continue to grow during the 21st century reaching 98 million in 2055. GDP projections are aligned with those from the World Economic Outlook of the IMF and the World Bank for the short term and from the OECD for the longer term. The long-term trajectory of GDP and GDP per capita reflects the transition of Türkiye to a high-income country. The average GDP growth rate is estimated at 3.8% in the period 2020-2030, 3.0% in 2030-2040, and 2.8% in 2040-2055. The Turkish economy is projected to grow to 1.5 trillion US \$’2015 in 2030 and double until 2055, reaching close to 3 trillion US\$’2015 (constant prices), while GDP per capita is projected to more than US\$ 30,000 in 2055 with an average growth rate of 2.7% in the 2020-2055 period.

Figure 1: Türkiye’s population and GDP development [4-7].

The projections on the sectoral value-added and structure of the economy are based on Türkiye’s 11th Development Plan [8] and the OECD macroeconomic outlook [6]. The services sector continues to dominate generating 66% of gross value added by 2050. Manufacturing retains its share, whilst a slight shift is projected from heavy industry towards more knowledge- and technology-intensive sub-sectors, such as engineering and pharmaceuticals. The share of the agricultural sector is projected to decline from 8% in 2020 to 5% in 2050.

Figure 2: Türkiye’s sectoral value-added projections [6,8].

Current emission situation

The GHG emissions of Türkiye grew steadily by 3.1% annually on average since 1990. This was primarily driven by the high increase of the fuel combustion activities in the energy sector that account for almost 71% of total GHGs based on 2021 national GHG inventory of the country. The key energy-related emitters are the energy industries, and the transport sector, owing to the economic development and the continuous population rise combined with increasing car ownership per capita.

Figure 3: Türkiye's GHG emissions by sector in 2012 & 2021 [9].

National targets (NDC) and programs/policies

Figure 4: Türkiye's key climate-related milestones.

net zero emissions by 2053. In 2023, Türkiye submitted the updated NDC, upscaling the 21% emissions reduction target to 41% by 2030. However, as shown in Figure 5, the specified baseline scenario of Türkiye's NDC assumes an acceleration of emissions growth until 2030, even higher than historical trends; this indicates that the NDC target of the country lacks ambition, as even if achieved it will lead to a continuation of historical developments, as shown in Figure 5, and implies that real transformation efforts will not be necessary at least in the current decade.

The Republic of Türkiye became Party to the UNFCCC in 2004. The country submitted its Intended Nationally Determined Contribution (INDC) to the UNFCCC in September 2015, in accordance with the decisions 1/CP.19 and 1/CP.20, and in line with the ultimate objective of the Convention set out in Article 2, by setting a greenhouse gas emissions reduction target of up to 21% by 2030 compared to a specified baseline scenario. Six years later (2021), Türkiye ratified and acceded to the legally binding Paris Agreement, and at the same year announced the vision to reach

In this context the national climate change mitigation policy is based on several national sector-specific legislative acts, strategies, and action plans, since as early as 2007, when the first Energy Efficiency Law was in force. Since then, the list of overarching policies and strategies included the 11th Development Plan for 2019-2023, the National Climate Change Strategy and the related Action Plan for 2010-2023, the Energy Efficiency Strategy and National Energy Efficiency Action Plan (2017-2023), the National Transport and Logistics Master Plan up to 2053, the Türkiye National Energy Plan (2020 - 2035) and the Hydrogen Technologies Roadmap of Türkiye in 2023. Currently, in 2024, the country is preparing the revision of Türkiye's Long-Term Climate Change Strategy as input to the UNFCCC.

In the recent years, significant investments have been materialized in the power sector, underpinned by the Renewable Energy Sources Support Mechanism (YEKDEM) and the By-Law on Renewable Energy Resource Areas (YEKA), leading to the acceleration of renewable energy investments, especially wind and solar power.

Figure 5: Türkiye's GHG emissions since 2012 and 2030 mitigation pledges.

Global conditions

Alongside country-specific socio-economic projections, key global levers influence the long-term energy planning of Türkiye. The global conditions factored in this study are the global fuel price trajectory, as Türkiye is a major hydrocarbon importer, the capital costs of cutting edge and emerging clean technologies as well as the regional and global policies setting the ambition for climate action.

The current brief uses the long-term estimates of international fossil fuel prices derived from the World Bank's Commodity Markets Outlook [10] and the Global Energy and Climate Outlook (GECO) report of the Joint Research Center [11]. This trajectory reflects long-term trends and does not capture short-term fluctuations in prices.

The evolution of the overnight capital costs for the low-carbon technologies both in the demand and the supply sectors, embedded in the study, is obtained from the EU Reference scenario 2020 [12] and the ASSET study [13], assuming downward trends till 2055, driven by accelerated learning-by-doing, innovation dynamics, economies of scale, and technology maturity.

EU policies, that would directly affect the exports of Türkiye such as Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM), or those stemming from climate action plans (Fit-for-55 package, REPowerEU, etc.), which should be adopted by all candidate countries for EU accessions, will also affect the transition roadmap of Türkiye.

Key decarbonization pathways & related transformations

The scope of the study is to assess the impacts of a plausible decarbonization pathway for the energy sector of Türkiye (NZES), compared to a reference case (REFS) until mid-of-the-century. The study used the modelling framework CompactPRIMES, which is a fully-fledged energy demand and supply model, designed and developed by E3-Modelling and customized to the specificities of the Turkish energy system. CompactPRIMES combines micro-economic foundations with engineering details, compatible with a long-term time scale and sectoral detail of available statistics for Türkiye. The model horizon for the current analysis is up to 2055, projections are on a 5-year timescale and include: detailed energy balances, demand of energy by sector, various energy saving possibilities in terms of energy efficiency, fuel mix by sector, power generation mix, investment and technology uptake, overall costs, consumer prices, emissions, as well as key energy and climate policies applied at national level.

The study covers the energy-related greenhouse gas emissions as well as the industrial non-energy related CO₂ emissions, apart from HFCs, PFCs and SF₆ derived from refrigeration, air-conditioning, semi-conductor industry, etc. The GHG emissions from Industrial Processes and Product Use (IPPU), Agriculture, Waste & Wastewater as well as Land Use, Land Use Change and Forestry (LULUCF) are beyond the scope of this analysis.

Comparison of policy relevant scenarios

The Reference Scenario (REFS) constitutes a stated policies scenario, which accounts for the existing policies adopted by 2021/2022. It embeds key strategic projects of the country, namely the commissioning of four units of the Akkuyu Nuclear Power Plant in 2025-2030. The Net Zero Emission scenario (NZES) constitutes a decarbonization roadmap for the energy sector of Türkiye, compatible with the 2030 NDC targets and the 2053 net-zero climate pledges of the country.

In the NZES scenario, total energy-related CO₂ emissions peak at 405 Mtons by 2025 and start to decrease in 2030 – a 10% decrease from 2018 levels. This is prompted by the displacement of solids (mostly coal and lignite) in the power sector, whereas the demand side still exhibits higher emissions than 2018. Clean energy transition policies in end-use sectors and in the power sector would drive considerable emission reductions after 2030, resulting in 56% by 2040 and 97% by 2055 reductions compared to 2018 levels. The introduction of strong climate policies forces solid-fired plants to be substituted by gas plants and renewables, reducing emissions by 44% in 2030 and by 86% in 2040. The power sector exhibits negative emissions by 2050, through the deployment of the Biomass gasification combined with Carbon Capture and Storage (BECCS) technology. The application of ambitious emission reduction policies, the massive electrification of energy end-uses, the gradual displacement of fossil gas by biomethane, green hydrogen and synthetic methane in the pipeline gas from 2035 onwards as well as the deployment of sustainable transportation technologies trigger the curbing of CO₂ emissions to almost zero by 2050 - 2055.

Figure 6: CO₂ emission reduction by sector vs Reference (left) – Sectoral CO₂ emission trajectory in NZES (right).

The emission gap of almost 13 Mtons in the energy sector, most of which stem from aviation and trucks, can be offset by either further abatements in Waste and Agriculture or higher removals from LULUCF or other Carbon Dioxide Removal technologies such as Direct Air Capture.

Key strategies to achieve the NDC and net-zero targets

Emission reduction in the power sector is a low-hanging fruit, owing to already mature and cost-efficient technologies and the high renewable energy potential of the country. Rising CO₂ prices and decreasing renewable technology costs challenge the cost competitiveness of thermal power plants. Innovative renewable technologies such as wind offshore enter the power mix and the emissions drop by 87% by 2040 in the power sector. Negative emissions are achieved with the use of BECCS toward the end of the projection period. Thermal processes in industry are hard to decarbonize as they require high-temperature heat and electrification currently faces technical and economic challenges. In industry, energy efficient technologies and heat recovery investments are deployed after 2030, and gas becomes a renewable option with almost zero carbon footprint in the long run owing to pipeline gas blending with zero-carbon gaseous fuels (including biomethane, hydrogen, and e-gas).

The residential and tertiary sectors achieve 48% and 42% emission reduction respectively by 2040 compared to 2018 levels. Deep renovation of old building stock and stricter building codes in newly built buildings, as well as the use of heat pumps for space heating are the key levers to decarbonize the buildings sector. The introduction of emission performance standards for new passenger vehicles and trucks plays a key role for the 37% decline of transport-related emissions by 2040. Towards 2055, all new road vehicles are carbon neutral. Advanced biofuels and synthetic kerosene are used at a high blending rate in aviation.

By 2050 – 2055 all sectors contribute significantly to emission reduction, reaching 91% and 97% respectively. Decarbonization is completed through gas blending by 2055.

Figure 7: Key milestones in the net zero emission scenario.

Sectoral system transformations

The Republic of Türkiye has declared net zero emissions as a national target for the year 2053 with a policy roadmap and milestones for getting there to be announced within 2024. The transition to climate neutrality requires the adoption of ambitious policy measures and clean technologies both in the demand and supply side of the energy system.

The CO₂ price is the policy driver of choice for reducing emissions in the power sector and industry, mimicking the price of the emission allowance of EU ETS. It is assumed to apply in the power and industrial sectors, as well as in aviation. Carbon pricing acts as a catalyst for the uptake of renewables in the power sector. The CO₂ price starts from a low level in 2025 (compared to the current EU ETS levels) but increases gradually after 2030. It was found that a CO₂ price between 250 and 320 USD/ton ensures compliance with the net zero target by 2050 – 2055, if combined with other climate measures and regulatory instruments (e.g. efficiency standards, building codes, blending mandates, CO₂ standards in vehicles etc.).

Subsidies as well as changes in the market design and the regulatory framework incentivize the utilization of renewables, energy efficiency and heat recovery investments in end-use sectors. New technologies such as heat pumps have significantly lower energy intensity compared to fossil fuel options but are associated with higher equipment costs. Nonetheless, learning rates drive the cost reduction of new low-carbon technologies in the future.

In the transport sector, emission performance standards apply for new vehicles, similarly to the relevant regulatory policy instrument in the EU. A mandate for zero emission vehicles should be enforced early enough (by 2040-2045) to comply with a decarbonization target by 2053, since transport vehicles are characterized by long lifespan.

Electrification and alternative fuels like Sustainable Aviation Fuels (SAFs), advanced biofuels, and ammonia play a prominent role in the decarbonization of aviation and maritime.

Natural gas currently represents 24 – 25% of final energy consumption in the country. In industry, gas can replace coal and oil in hard-to-electrify thermal uses, like cement kilns. Blending natural gas with carbon-free fuels in the pipeline is an option for decarbonizing the hard-to-electrify industrial processes, such as those associated with high temperatures in industry. Clean gas can either be biomethane, or e-fuels such as green hydrogen and synthetic methane. It is assumed that gas blending is back-loaded beginning of 2035, with small shares of clean gases at the gas mix initially. The shares expand rapidly during 2040 – 2050, leading to almost zero carbon content by 2050 – 2055 in line with the country's net-zero goal for 2053.

Industry

Energy consumption in industry decouples from Reference scenario trends post 2030, achieving a 24.4% reduction by 2045 and 28.3% by 2050. Efficiency comes primarily from non-metallic minerals, where final energy consumption drops by 43% in the long run compared to the Reference scenario. This is made possible by exploiting the untapped efficiency potential in the cement sector, which includes the recovery of waste heat, and making thermal processes more efficient, by reducing the *clinker to cement* ratio.

In the metal industry, final energy consumption decreases by 12-13% in the long run, reflecting limitations for further improvements in the steel industry. Electric arc furnaces, which are far more efficient than blast furnaces, represented 70% of total steel production by 2020. It is assumed that their share increases further by 10 percentage points already under Reference scenario conditions, thus limiting the potential for further efficiency gains in the net-zero scenario. From 2035 onwards, blast furnace factories are gradually substituted by new steel factories that use direct-reduced iron. Although this technology does not provide significant efficiency gains, it introduces green hydrogen and pipeline gas in the process of iron ore reduction. In the remaining industrial sectors, final energy consumption decreases approximately by 17% by 2040 and 25% in the long run attributed to heat recovery combined with efficient equipment.

Between 2040-2055 the electrification of industrial uses and resulting efficiency gains curb the use of conventional fuels. 48% of final energy consumption by 2055 in industry comes from electricity compared to around 29% in 2020.

Source: CompactPRIMES

Figure 8: Final energy consumption in industry by energy carrier.

Transportation

Transport accounts for 42.5% of CO₂ emissions in the demand sectors and for 22.1% of economy-wide CO₂ emissions, with a rapid increase in recent decades. It is therefore an area where policy efforts need to intensify.

Energy efficiency improvements in transport depend strongly on the uptake of more efficient technologies and in particular electric vehicles that currently use on average 70% less energy per vehicle-kilometer compared to a conventional car. Technological progress and learning-by-doing have positive effects on the reduction of final energy demand. The uptake of zero-emission private cars (electric, fuel cell) is led mainly by the imposition of stringent emission standards and regulations that ensure no new internal combustion engine vehicles are sold after 2040.

Battery-electric, Plug-in Hybrid and fuel cell private cars dominate the car fleet in 2055. These measures are further enhanced by the increase in the availability and use of sustainable low-carbon fuels across the road sector, such as biodiesel and bio-gasoline, especially in sector that are hard to electrify (e.g. aviation, shipping).

Figure 9: Stock of passenger cars (left) and of freight trucks by technology type (right).

Modal shift is another driver of transport decarbonization. In 2018 public road transport accounted for 59% of the total passenger transport in Türkiye, associated with the low levels of car ownership (150 cars per 1000 inhabitants approximately). Economic growth in the Reference scenario would lead to higher shares of private passenger transport activity compared to public road transport. In the NZES, modal shift is assumed between the road and the rail sector. This assumption is in line with the *Transport and Logistics Master Plan* of the Turkish Ministry of Transport and Infrastructure [14], where Türkiye emerges as a hub for logistics. The electrification of the rail sector is also prominent, owing primarily to the mobilization of investments in electrified rapid rail lines.

In other transport sectors that are hard to decarbonize, such as aviation and navigation, policies that favor the blending of low-carbon fuels are critical. In aviation, a mandatory blending of biokerosene has been considered by 2055, while in navigation, renewable ammonia is introduced in the energy mix in 2040 onwards along with green hydrogen (70% ammonia - 30% hydrogen). Using ammonia as a marine fuel can become the backbone of maritime decarbonization but for this to happen technical and regulatory measures need to be adopted.

Figure 10: Final energy consumption in transportation sector by energy carrier.

Buildings

The energy demand for heating and cooling purposes is projected to decline from 2025 onwards driven by intensive renovation interventions and the penetration of heat pumps that have much higher efficiency compared to conventional heating systems. Energy saving efforts accelerate in the period 2025-2040. Deep retrofitting programs that focus on the building envelope – insulation of the facade, of the roof and external walls, installation of multiple pane windows, etc. – and several programmes targeting the services sector, and especially the government-owned buildings, lead to annual energy savings of 2.8% on average from 2030 to 2055 compared to the Reference scenario. Additionally, the penetration of advanced more efficient technologies in all end-uses coupled with the increased market deployment of efficient heat pumps would also result in large energy savings.

The deep decarbonization of the buildings sector will not be possible without harnessing the significant RES potential, which remains largely untapped, especially with regards to geothermal energy, solar energy, and

biomass. The geological conditions in the Alpine-Himalayan orogenic belt endow Türkiye with high geothermal potential. More specifically, about 450 geothermal fields have been discovered (mainly by the General Directorate of Mineral Research and Exploration (MTA) and the private sector) in Türkiye [15]. Geothermal energy is a cost-effective option in regions where it is not possible to heat greenhouses by using traditional methods (due to climatic change). Furthermore, the share of solar energy in the final energy consumption of households experiences a seven-fold increase (19.6%) by 2055 compared to 2020 levels (2.9%), stimulated by the wide market uptake of solar thermal water heaters.

Starting from 2035, blending of clean gaseous fuels is assumed to take place in the gas grid, substituting the imported natural gas by synthetic methane (clean gas), hydrogen and biogas. This serves multiple purposes, among which, the utilization of the existing gas infrastructure and the reduction of carbon emissions.

Figure 11: Final energy consumption in residential (left) and tertiary (right) sectors by energy carrier.

Energy supply system

Demand for electricity roughly follows the REFS trends until 2035 but intensifies afterwards, driven by high electrification rates in transport, industry, and buildings sectors. Demand for green hydrogen in various forms, either for direct consumption, or for blending in gas pipelines or for synthetic fuel production increases considerably the gross electricity demand in the long run.

Moderate CO₂ prices, i.e., 30 USD/ton, would reduce the use of solids in electricity generation, but fail to bring about the earlier decommissioning of coal power stations. Coal phase out takes place by 2035 - 2040, as a result of higher CO₂ prices (but still not reaching the levels of EU ETS). Nevertheless, part of these plants is used as cold reserves. Solids plants are partially substituted by gas plants in the medium term, producing more than 100 TWh by 2035. The Akkuyu nuclear power plant is fully commissioned by 2030. A similar station is commissioned by 2040 – 2045, increasing the overall nuclear-based electricity by 76 TWh, accounting for almost 8 - 10% of total electricity generation throughout the projection period. Solar power generation reaches 350 TWh, or 41% of total domestic power generation by 2050. Wind plants, onshore and offshore, produce 265 TWh, or 31% of total by 2050.

Growing electricity demand and RES expansion lead to an almost five-fold expansion of gross power capacity by 2055 compared to 2018 levels, dominated by solar PV plants. Huge investments in renewables imply a faster pace

for capital expenditures and entail significant technical challenges linked with the intermittency and seasonality of the power generation profile, among which the high balancing, reserve and storage requirements, as well as a robust power grid infrastructure.

On-shore wind plants are constrained by the limited potential reaching 43.5 GW by 2055. The first wind-offshore power plants are commissioned by 2035. Offshore capacity is 17 GW by 2040 and reaches 43 GW by 2055. With the deployment of Akkuyu and Sinope power stations, nuclear gross capacity amounts to 10 GW by 2045. Balancing and reserves requirements are satisfied mainly by Combined Cycle Gas Turbines (CCGT), gas turbines (GT) or gas with CCS power plants. The BECCS unit of 660 MW is installed by 2045. This unit is subsidized and helps the power system achieve negative GHG emissions.

Storage is key to unlocking the renewable power's full potential, solar PV in particular. As demand for hydrogen is considered flexible, it absorbs a fraction of the surplus electricity generation by renewable plants, while the remaining surplus is stored in batteries. The total installed capacity of electrolyzers reaches 32 GW by 2040 and 82 GW by 2055, while that of battery storage is 21 GW by 2055.

Figure 12: Evolution of gross power generation (left) and power capacity (right) by plant type.

Key messages for next NDCs

Türkiye became Party to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change in 2004 and to the Kyoto Protocol in 2009. Türkiye ratified the Paris Agreement in 2021 and in October of the same year announced the 2053 carbon neutrality goal. The economy of the country is carbon intensive as it relies mainly on the use of fossil fuels and very limited progress has been made so far in reducing emissions.

Our analysis indicates that the NDC target of Türkiye can be achieved with relatively limited climate effort by 2030 as the emissions reduction goal is not ambitious compared to historical developments. So, the next Türkiye's NDC should include a more ambitious emissions reduction target for 2030/2035 to pave the way towards the long-term transformations in major emitting sectors (energy supply, transport, industries, buildings) required to achieve net-

zero emissions by mid-century. By implementing ambitious and targeted climate policies as part of its next NDC, Türkiye will be able to decarbonize its economy, reduce its reliance on imported fossil fuels, diversify its energy mix, reduced its energy import dependence, and also achieve the long-term target of net zero emissions by 2053. This will be accomplished by the accelerated development of renewable energy sources, electrification of energy end-uses, and strong energy efficiency improvements, combined with the emergence of novel technologies (including hydrogen and CCS) to decarbonize hard to abate sectors. The study shows that the decarbonization of an emerging, highly industrialized economy like Türkiye, with sustained rates of economic growth and rising population is feasible, albeit challenging, especially given its current strong dependence on imported fossil fuels.

The implementation of NDC and long-term decarbonization should be guided by targeted policies and regulatory framework that encourages investments in energy efficiency, renewable power and disruptive clean energy technologies. The sectors that offer the highest and most cost-efficient potential for emissions reductions are the buildings and the power supply sectors, while specific transport segments and heavy industries require the uptake of currently immature technologies (e.g. advanced biofuels, hydrogen, synthetic e-fuels, CCS). The role of hydrogen, as an energy carrier, is crucial for decarbonizing energy uses, as it takes advantage of existing infrastructure and is used in hard-to-decarbonize industrial processes, such as steel and cement industry, while synthetic e-fuels and advanced biofuels are used to decarbonize the gas grid and hard-to-electrify transport modes (shipping, aviation).

An important challenge that Türkiye needs to overcome on its pathway towards decarbonization concerns the fast growth of energy demand triggered by increasing population, economic growth and rising standards of living that should be covered by low- and zero-carbon energy sources. Energy efficiency improvements should be therefore prioritized in the country across all demand sectors (transport, buildings, industries) to reduce the requirements for the deployment of new, capital intensive technologies and relevant infrastructure. While the large uptake of solar and wind power is a cost-efficient solution to decarbonize the power grid, other zero-carbon options should also be upscaled, including nuclear power, biomass, green hydrogen, and Carbon Capture and Storage; however all these options face several socio-political, financial, technical, and environmental challenges that should be dealt with to ensure their efficient implementation in the country.

Türkiye is a major importer of fossil fuels, thus having a strong incentive to reduce its energy import dependence and develop clean energy technologies domestically. At the same time, Türkiye is vulnerable to the effects of climate change, with its agricultural sector severely impacted by droughts, thus decreasing production, and having potential consequences on food security. The frequency of extreme weather events in Türkiye has also increased alarmingly, with heatwaves and floods threatening the health of citizens. Therefore, Türkiye should raise its climate policy ambitions, and submit an updated NDC document, with significantly strengthened GHG emissions reduction targets for 2030/2035. The country should phase out fossil fuels in the upcoming decades, and rapidly increase the uptake of renewable energy sources and energy efficiency. This will ensure a prosperous future for the Turkish people, and the rest of humanity, in alignment with the Paris Agreement goal of 1.5°C temperature increase limit.

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COUNTRY REPORT

Transition pathways for TÜRKIYE

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